

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

MODELS AND ALGORITHM FOR INTEGRAL RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT OF THE TELECOMMUNICATION INFRASTRUCTURE ACCOUNTING SYSTEM

Makhmudov M.

Director, PhD, LLC UNICON.UZ

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ORCID: 0009-0002-8838-5277

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19922815>

Abstract

This article considers the problem of quantitatively assessing the reliability of a telecommunications infrastructure accounting system as a complex service comprising technical, information, and process components. An approach is proposed in which the integral reliability of the cadastral service is determined through a combined consideration of the IT infrastructure readiness, the information reliability of the data, and the sustainability of the support processes. Probabilistic dependencies, an information reliability index, a Markov model of the support process states, and parameter estimates obtained directly from operational change logs, updates, and audit results are used to calculate the partial and integral indicators. An algorithm for sequential processing of the initial data is presented, oriented toward practical application in real-life cadastral systems. A sensitivity analysis is performed to determine the impact of update intensity and error probability on the steady-state reliability of the data. An example of applying the method to compare the basic and improved cadastral service support scenarios is given.

Keywords: reliability, telecommunication infrastructure, digital cadastre, cadastral service, operational logs, data audit, Markov model, information reliability, scenario analysis, parameter assessment.

Introduction

The development of the telecommunications industry is accompanied by a constant expansion of infrastructure facilities, increasing complexity of network architecture, and increasing demands on the reliability of the data used to make technical and management decisions. Under these conditions, a telecommunications infrastructure asset tracking system is no longer just a record archive and is becoming an effective tool for network maintenance, modernization planning, operational status monitoring, and reporting.

Experience shows that deterioration in the quality of such a service occurs not only due to failures of servers, communication channels, or software components. Equally significant are the obsolescence of records, data entry and reconciliation errors, and violations of update and verification procedures. For this reason, assessing the reliability of a cadastral service requires consideration of several interrelated components, each of which affects the final result.

Existing telecommunications infrastructure maintenance systems often assess only the availability

of the software and hardware environment. However, even with high availability of IT components, the service may remain virtually unusable if information on coordinates, object types, connection topology, or equipment parameters is outdated or contains errors. Therefore, the task must be broader: an indicator is needed that reflects the state of the service as a whole.

1. Statement of the problem and structure of the integral indicator

The integral reliability of a cadastral service is considered as the combined probability of the correct functioning of three components: the IT infrastructure, the information dataset, and the support processes. This approach reflects a real-world operational situation: the failure or degradation of any of these components leads to a reduction in service quality, even if the others are functioning normally.

If we accept the conditional factorization of the event of correct functioning of the service through conditional probabilities, then the integral reliability of the cadastral service is determined by the expression:

$$R_{CS}(t) = P\{\varepsilon_{IT}(t)\} \cdot P\{\varepsilon_D(t) | \varepsilon_{IT}(t)\} \cdot P\{\varepsilon_P(t) | \varepsilon_{IT}(t) \cap \varepsilon_D(t)\}. \quad (1)$$

Let's introduce the following notations:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{IT}(t) &= P\{\varepsilon_{IT}(t)\}, \\ R_D(t) &= P\{\varepsilon_D(t) | \varepsilon_{IT}(t)\}, \\ R_P(t) &= P\{\varepsilon_P(t) | \varepsilon_{IT}(t) \cap \varepsilon_D(t)\}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Then the integral indicator takes a more compact form:

$$R_{CS}(t) = R_{IT}(t) \cdot R_D(t) \cdot R_P(t). \quad (3)$$

Expression (3) is convenient because it allows for the separate calculation of individual indicators, analysis of the contribution of each component, and then the final probabilistic assessment. At the same time, the indicator structure itself retains a strict meaning: service reliability is high only when the technical environment, data accuracy, and acceptable maintenance processes are simultaneously ensured.

2. Information component of reliability

To assess the state of data in the accounting system, an index of information reliability is introduced, defined as a weighted geometric mean of the normalized characteristics of completeness, relevance, topological consistency and spatial accuracy:

$$I_{\text{inf}} = \left(C^\alpha \cdot A^\beta \cdot T^\gamma \cdot S^\delta \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha+\beta+\gamma+\delta}} \cdot p(t) \cdot (1-\varepsilon), \quad (4)$$

where $C, A, T, S \in [0; 1]$ - normalized data quality indicators;

$\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ - weighting coefficients reflecting the priorities of a specific type of infrastructure facilities;

$p(t)$ - function that takes into account the influence of time on the state of records;

ε - probability of errors in data input, processing or reconciliation.

This representation allows for the heterogeneity of telecommunications infrastructure objects to be taken into account. For some network elements, topological consistency is more sensitive, while for others, the accuracy of coordinate descriptions, elevation marks, or placement parameters is more important. A weighted geometric mean is preferable in this case because a decrease in one component is immediately reflected in the overall result and is not fully offset by higher values of other indicators.

I_{inf} index is introduced not as an abstract value, but as a measurable characteristic of data quality suitable for regular monitoring. It can be calculated for an individual object, a set of objects, a network segment, an administrative territory, or the entire system.

3. Assessing the reliability of support processes

Maintenance of the cadastral service involves transitions between permissible and inadmissible states. A continuous Markov model is used to describe this aspect. Let $P_i(t)$ be the probability of the system

$$R_{\text{CS.CTRL}}(t) = \omega_1 R_{\text{IT}}(t) + \omega_2 I_{\text{inf}}(t) + \omega_3 I_{\text{proc}}(t), \quad \omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_3 = 1. \quad (9)$$

where $\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3$ - weights assigned in accordance with regulatory requirements and operational priorities;

$I_{\text{proc}}(t)$ - normalized quality assessment of the process component.

Unlike expression (8), which uses a product and maintains a strict probabilistic interpretation, index (9) is convenient for organizational and management analysis, comparison of departments, monitoring compliance with regulations, and constructing KPIs.

5. Computational pipeline and practical calculation algorithm

being in state S_i at time t . Then the dynamics of the state probability vector are determined by the Kolmogorov equation:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{P}(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{P}(t)\mathbf{Q}, \quad \mathbf{P}(0)=\mathbf{P}_0. \quad (5)$$

The solution to the system can be written in matrix form:

$$\mathbf{P}(t) = \mathbf{P}(0)e^{\mathbf{Q}t}. \quad (6)$$

The reliability of support processes is determined by the probability of the system being in acceptable states S_0 or S_1 :

$$R_P(t) = P_0(t) + P_1(t) = 1 - P_2(t) - P_3(t). \quad (7)$$

This description allows for the dynamic nature of maintenance procedures to be taken into account. The system may be in normal mode, in a partially degraded state, in a state of accumulating errors, or in a state in which correct service provision has already been disrupted. The Markov model allows for the transition from a verbal description of these modes to a computational model in which the state of processes is expressed through the probabilities of transitions between them.

4. Integrated probabilistic and management assessment

Taking into account expressions (3), (4) and (7), the integral probabilistic assessment of the reliability of the cadastral service will be written as:

$$R_{\text{CS}}(t) = R_{\text{IT}}(t) \cdot I_{\text{inf}}(t) \cdot R_P(t). \quad (8)$$

Indicator (8) reflects the probability that at time t the service as a whole remains suitable for correct operation. In other words, three conditions must be met simultaneously: the IT infrastructure is accessible, the data is in an acceptable information state, and the maintenance processes have not exceeded their operating limits.

In addition, operational practice requires an indicator that is convenient for reporting, comparing support options, and setting priorities in accordance with current regulations. For these purposes, a management integrated index is being introduced:

Integrated reliability indicators cannot be obtained without a parameter assessment procedure based on actual operating data. In a real system, they are not predefined, but are reconstructed from object change logs, record updates, inspection reports, monitoring data, and audit materials.

This sequence ensures the reproducibility of calculations and makes the method suitable for regular use in existing information systems. Crucially, the calculations are performed not on abstract parameters, but on information already present in the network's maintenance circuits.

Pic. 1 – Computational pipeline for assessing the reliability of the cadastral service of the digital cadastre

The flows of infrastructure changes and cadastral record updates are described by Poisson processes. If during the observation period T , N_0 object changes and N_u record updates are recorded, then the maximum likelihood estimates of the intensities are as follows:

$$\hat{\lambda}_0 = \frac{N_0}{T}, \quad \hat{\lambda}_u = \frac{N_u}{T}. \quad (10)$$

The probability of data entry, processing, or reconciliation errors is assessed based on the results of verification and audit. If N_{err} errors are detected in N_{chk} checks, then:

$$\hat{\varepsilon} = \frac{N_{err}}{N_{chk}}. \quad (11)$$

The Markov model of process control uses event logs that record transitions between states. If N_{ij} transitions $S_i \rightarrow S_j$ are recorded, and the total time spent in state S_i is T_i , then the transition intensity is determined by the expression

$$\hat{\lambda}_{ij} = \frac{N_{ij}}{T_i}. \quad (12)$$

The resulting estimates naturally link the model to the system's actual operating mode. This allows not only to calculate current indicator values but also to perform recalculations over a sliding time window, tracking changes in reliability as the maintenance discipline changes.

Pic. 2 – Integrated assessment of the reliability of the cadastral service based on operational logs and audit data

This algorithm is convenient because it combines technical, informational, and organizational components into a single procedure. It is suitable for both periodic reporting and for assessing the impact of proposed changes to support regulations.

6. Sensitivity analysis and scenario modeling

Once the integrated indicators have been obtained, a practical question arises regarding which measures actually yield a significant increase in reliability and which lead to only minor changes.

Let us consider the influence of the intensity of updating cadastral records on the steady-state reliability of data. Differentiation by the parameter λ_u , which characterizes the frequency of updates, yields:

$$\frac{\partial R_D^{(\infty)}}{\partial \lambda_u} = (1 - \varepsilon) \cdot \frac{\lambda_0}{(\lambda_0 + \lambda_u)^2}, \quad (13)$$

where λ_0 - intensity of change of an object;

λ_u - intensity of updating the cadastral record.

From expression (13), it follows that the greatest effect from increasing update frequency is observed in cases where the infrastructure changes quite intensively, and updates are performed with moderate regularity. It is precisely in areas where maintenance discipline is still insufficient that further strengthening of regulations yields the greatest benefit.

Pic. 3 – Sensitivity of stationary data reliability to update intensity for different λ_0

Now let's consider the influence of the probability of input and processing errors. The sensitivity of the steady-state reliability of data with respect to the parameter ε is determined by the relation

$$\frac{\partial R_D^{(\infty)}}{\partial \varepsilon} = - \frac{\lambda_u}{\lambda_0 + \lambda_u}. \quad (14)$$

The resulting expression demonstrates that improving quality control procedures directly impacts the overall reliability of data. The more regular updates are performed, the more noticeable the negative impact of errors and the greater the value of high-quality verification.

Pic. 4 – Sensitivity of data reliability to the parameter ε for λ_u

The analysis concludes with a comparison of individual and integrated reliability indicators in the baseline and improved scenarios. The most noticeable changes are driven by the growth of information and process components, while the readiness of the IT infrastructure remains virtually unchanged.

Pic. 5

Comparison of cadastral service reliability indicators in the basic and improved scenarios ($t = 6$ months)

7. An example of application of the proposed method

Let us consider an illustrative example consistent with the dependencies given in the article. Let the partial reliability indicators be estimated over an observation interval of $T= 6$ months: for the baseline scenario $R_{rr} = 0.99$; $I_{inf} = 0.50$; $R_p = 0.85$; for the improved scenario $R_{rr} = 0.99$; $I_{inf} = 0.63$; $R_p = 0.88$.

Then, according to expression (8), the integral reliability of the cadastral service is for the base scenario:

$$R_{CS(base)} = 0.99 \cdot 0.50 \cdot 0.85 = 0.42075 \approx 0.42,$$

and for the improved scenario:

$$R_{CS(imp)} = 0.99 \cdot 0.63 \cdot 0.88 = 0.54886 \approx 0.55.$$

Consequently, strengthening the maintenance and audit regulations leads to an increase in the integral reliability by approximately 0.13, that is, by more than 30% relative to the initial level.

Let's consider the impact of update and error parameters on steady-state data reliability. Let's assume that in the initial mode, the object change rate is $\lambda_0 = 0.2$ [1/month], the update rate is $\lambda_u = 0.4$ [1/month], and the error probability is $\varepsilon = 0.05$. Then, from expression (13),

we obtain $\frac{\partial R_D^{(\infty)}}{\partial \lambda_u} \approx 0.528$. This means that, at this operating point, increasing the update frequency still yields a significant increase in steady-state data reliability.

According to expression (14), we have $\frac{\partial R_D^{(\infty)}}{\partial \varepsilon}$

$= -0.667$. This value demonstrates that even a moderate error rate during regular updates significantly reduces data reliability. This leads to a practically important conclusion: simply increasing the update frequency without improving quality control does not fully improve the overall reliability of the service.

If for the management analysis we adopt the weights $\omega_1 = 0.3$, $\omega_2 = 0.4$, $\omega_3 = 0.3$, and set the normalized process assessment equal to $I_{proc(base)} = 0.65$ for the base scenario and $I_{proc(imp)} = 0.74$ for the improved scenario, then according to expression (9) we obtain $R_{CS,CTRL(base)} = 0.692$ and $R_{CS,CTRL(imp)} = 0.771$. Thus, the probabilistic and management assessments consistently

show the same direction of change: the reserve for increasing reliability is concentrated primarily in the area of data quality and support processes.

8. Discussion of results

The proposed method doesn't limit the reliability of a cadastral service to the availability of the software and hardware platform alone. This is particularly important for telecommunications infrastructure accounting systems, as the technical integrity of servers and communication channels alone does not guarantee the operational usefulness of the result.

The second key feature of the approach is that its parameters are estimated using actual change logs, updates, and checks. This makes the calculations reproducible and allows the model to be tailored to a specific system, rather than relying on generic assumptions that have little bearing on real-world practice.

Equally important is the algorithm's scenario framework. It allows the method to be used not only to document the current state but also to justify management actions: strengthening auditing, reducing update intervals, changing audit procedures, and redistributing responsibilities between departments. In other words, the reliability indicator ceases to be merely a reporting value and becomes a decision-making tool.

The results of the sensitivity analysis confirm that the most significant effect is achieved through coordinated improvements in two areas: update regularity and quality of control. A unilateral strengthening of one of these areas inevitably encounters limitations. This explains the difference between the growth of individual indicators and the overall value of the service's overall reliability.

Conclusion

The article discusses about models and algorithm for the integrated assessment of the reliability of a telecommunications infrastructure facility accounting system, based on the combined consideration of three components: the readiness of the IT infrastructure, the information state of the data, and the sustainability of the support processes.

It is shown that an integrated probabilistic assessment of the reliability of a cadastral service can be represented as a product of partial components. For monitoring and reporting purposes, it is also advisable to use

a standardized management index with adjustable weights. To describe the information component, an information reliability index is introduced, taking into account completeness, relevance, topological consistency, spatial accuracy, and error probability. The process component is described using a continuous Markov model, allowing for the calculation of the probability of the system operating in acceptable modes.

A consistent computational procedure is proposed that links operational logs and audit data with parameter assessment, calculation of partial indicators, and derivation of integral service characteristics. A sensitivity analysis revealed that the greatest potential for improving reliability lies in data update discipline and the quality of control procedures. A case study of the method's application confirmed that strengthening maintenance and audit procedures leads to a significant increase in the integral reliability of the cadastral service.

The presented approach can be used in existing digital accounting systems of telecommunications infrastructure both for periodic assessment of the current state and for substantiating decisions on improving the processes of maintenance, verification and updating of data.

References:

1. Wang, R. Y., Strong, D. M. Beyond Accuracy: What Data Quality Means to Data Consumers // *Journal of Management Information Systems*. 1996. Vol. 12, No. 4. P. 5–33. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.1996.11518099>.
2. Wand, Y., Wang, R. Y. Anchoring Data Quality Dimensions in Ontological Foundations // *Communications of the ACM*. 1996. Vol. 39, No. 11. P. 86–95. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/240455.240479>.
3. Lee, Y. W., Strong, D. M., Kahn, B. K., Wang, R. Y. AIMQ: A Methodology for Information Quality Assessment // *Information & Management*. 2002. Vol. 40, No. 2. P. 133–146. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7206\(02\)00043-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7206(02)00043-5).
4. Strong, D. M. Information Quality: Managing Information as a Product // In: *Encyclopedia of Database Systems*. Springer, 2009. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-39940-9_497.
5. Batini, C., Scannapieco, M. *Data Quality: Concepts, Methodologies and Techniques*. Berlin; Heidelberg: Springer, 2006. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-33173-5>.
6. Batini, C., Scannapieco, M. *Data and Information Quality: Dimensions, Principles and Techniques*. Cham: Springer, 2016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24106-7>.
7. Heinrich, B., Klier, M. Metric-based Data Quality Assessment — Developing and Evaluating a Probability-based Currency Metric // *Decision Support Systems*. 2015. Vol. 72. P. 82–96. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2015.02.009>.
8. Heinrich, B., Hristova, D., Klier, M., Schiller, A., Szubartowicz, M. Requirements for Data Quality Metrics // *Journal of Data and Information Quality*. 2018. Vol. 9, No. 2. P. 1–32. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3148238>.
9. ISO/IEC 25012:2008. Software engineering — Software product Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — Data quality model. Official link: <https://www.iso.org/standard/35736.html>.
10. ISO 8000-1:2022. Data quality — Part 1: Overview. Official link: <https://www.iso.org/standard/81745.html>.
11. ITU-T Recommendation E.800. Definitions of terms related to quality of service / dependability vocabulary. Official link: <https://www.itu.int/rec/t-rec-e.800>
12. Trivedi, K. S., Bobbio, A. *Reliability and Availability Engineering: Modeling, Analysis, and Applications*. Cambridge University Press, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316163047>.
13. Bobbio, A., Bonanni, G., Ciancamerla, E., Clemente, R., Iacomini, A., Minichino, M., Scarlatti, A., Terruggia, R., Zendri, E. Unavailability of Critical SCADA Communication Links Interconnecting a Power Grid and a Telco Network // *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*. 2010. Vol. 95, No. 12. P. 1345–1357. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2010.06.011>.
14. Brous, P., Overtoom, I., Herder, P., Versluis, A., Janssen, M. Data Infrastructures for Asset Management Viewed as Complex Adaptive Systems // *Procedia Computer Science*. 2014. Vol. 36. P. 124–130. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2014.09.048>.
15. Višnjevac, N., Šošković, M., Mihajlović, R. Towards Quality Management Procedures in 3D Cadastre // *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*. 2024. Vol. 13, No. 5. Art. 160. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi13050160>.
16. Herrick, D. R. CMDDB Assessment and Remediation // *Proceedings of the 2023 ACM SIGUCCS Annual Conference*. 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3539811.3579551>.